

UTILIZATION OF FLAX FIBERS AND GLASS FIBERS IN A BIO-BASED RESIN

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the utilization of bio-based materials either as a bio-based resin or natural fibers in composites has emerged due to the need for better chemical sustainability. In addition, the sustainable use of chemicals has a potential positive impact on the environment. Moreover, the north portion of the USA is a rich source of renewable resources; therefore, developing polymers from cheap and renewable resources is cost effective. Some other advantages of using renewable resources in composite industry included: less dependence on petroleum-based products and higher specific strength and stiffness.

In this study, a new highly functional bio-based polyol is applied to create structural biocomposites. Bio-based polyols are reacted with polyisocyanates to generate polyurethanes. The resultant polyurethane from this novel high functionality bio-based polyol has shown higher moduli, hardness, and T_g compared to another bio-based and petroleum based polyols [1] [2]. Flax fibers were used in this study, because they possess moderate strength and low density [3]. Moreover, in comparison to other natural fibers, they are more readily available.

Polyurethanes (PURs) are usually made from petroleum based polyols and isocyanates and have widespread applications in automotive parts, coatings, sealants, adhesives and other infrastructure uses [4]. Today, polyurethanes are finding a growing interest for applications as composites due to the increasing demand for lightweight, durable and cost effective compounds for sectors such as the automotive market[5]. Owing to the versatility of polyurethane chemistry, a broad range of properties and applications are possible for reinforced composites, such as seat frames, sun shades, door panels, package trays and truck box panels. Adhesion between the polyurethane matrix and the fiber surface is also an important factor in the

improvement of mechanical performances [6]. Petrochemical-based polyester, polyether, and acrylic polyols are the main types of polyols used in PUs, but interest in plant oil-based polyols is growing [1, 2, 7].

Natural oils are a rich source of polymer precursors with broad ranges of properties. The wide ranges of properties in bio-based polymer are attributed to different types of functionalities of polymer precursors such as double bond and ester groups. Epoxidation is one of the most important functionalization reactions of double bonds, and epoxide ring-opening reactions can lead to numerous products [8]. On the other hand, the modification of double bonds can incorporate the functionalities like maleates, hydroxyl or epoxy [9] [10] [11, 12]. In the last decade, the development of bio-based polyols made from natural oils has received focused attention in polymer production. Hydroxyl-containing polyols and isocyanates are the two major components of polyurethane (PU). Therefore, developing the bio-based polyol for polyurethane manufacturing is also preferable due to economic and environmental issues.

Desroches' review on vegetable oil derived biopolyurethanes presents a detailed overview of different possible synthetic routes and includes a useful list of commercial bio-based polyols that can be applied in the production of polyurethanes [13]. Indeed, castor oil, a hydroxyl -containing triglyceride and other plant oils have been used for making polyol functional compounds [14]. Castor oil was the first natural oil that was used for making bio-based polyols. Several works have reported on the use of alcoholized castor oil for the production of polyurethanes obtained by polycondensation reactions with different isocyanate components [11] [15]. The polyurethane made from castor oil is relatively soft since the number of hydroxy groups per molecule is relatively low with only 2.7 per molecule on average. To improve the mechanical

properties of polyurethane, higher functionalities of polyol is needed [2, 16]. Among all of the available plant oils, soybean oil-based polyols are more desirable because they provide higher functionalities of polyol and result in better mechanical properties compared to other plant oil polyols. Moreover, it can be produced in large production volume abundance (ca. 70 million metric tons/year in USA) and low price (ca. 0.1 US \$/kg). Khot et al. utilized an acrylated epoxidized soybean oil to produce glass fiber composites by resin transfer molding [9]. Depending on the fiber content, young's moduli of 5.2 to 24.8 GPa were measured for the composites bearing 35 and 50 wt.% of GF, respectively, and tensile strengths of 129–463 MPa, for the same samples.

A common method to produce a bio-based polyol with higher functionalities is presented by previous researchers [1, 2] [17]. Two reaction steps in this method are epoxidization of soybean oil and then ring-opening with an active hydrogen molecule. However, we have recently produced a highly functionality epoxidized sucrose soyate polyol is called methoxylated sucrose soyate polyol (MSSP). When the ring-opening of epoxidized sucrose soyate (ESS) is accomplished using methanol, the resultant polyol is called methoxylated sucrose soyate polyol (MSSP). The schematic chemical structure of the methoxylated sucrose soyate polyol is shown in Fig.1. The use of an epoxidized sucrose ester of soybean oil gives even higher hydroxyl functionality and as a result, it provides superior properties compared to epoxidized soybean oil [2].

While we know this high hydroxyl group functionality polyol provides greater hardness and range of cross-link density to PU thermosets in coatings applications [1] [2], the potential application of this novel bio-polyol in polyurethane reinforcing composites has not been explored yet. This study examined two composites: (1) 50 % vol. glass/bio-based PU, (2) 40 % vol. flax/bio-based PU. The mechanical and thermal properties were assessed for this novel bio-based polyurethane and on the synthetic and natural fiber reinforced composites to confirm that they have desirable properties.

The tensile, flexural, shear, and impact strength in addition to thermal properties (HDT, T_g) of flax and glass fiber reinforced polyurethane (PU) derived from sucrose soyate resin composites were investigated herein.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material Preparation

Two types of fiber reinforcement and one type of polyurethane (PU) matrix were used in this study. The high functionality methoxylated sucrose soyate polyol (MSSP) for was prepared by epoxide ring-opening reactions from epoxidized sucrose ester of soybean oil—epoxidized sucrose soyate—in which secondary hydroxyl groups were generated from epoxides on fatty acid chains as reported previously [16]. This high functionality polyol contains OH eq. wt. = 300 g OH eq⁻¹. The isocyanate component is Baydur PUL 2500 Comp. A Isocyanate with an NCO content of 31.5%. The reinforcement used in this study was E-glass fabric with 237 g/cm² and plain weave supplied by Fibre Glast Development Corporation.

2.2 Composite Preparation

E-glass fibers and flax fibers were dried at 100 °C overnight to prevent void formation. The hand lay-up technique was used to prepare two fiber reinforced composites: (1) 40 vol. % flax/PU composite and (2) 50 vol.% glass/PU composite. Each layer of fiber fabric was pre-impregnated by matrix and then placed over the other fabric in the mold to ensure resin is uniformly distributed throughout the composite.

Composites were processed in the 100 mm x 200 mm dimension closed mold compression at room temperature under 110 kN for 12 hours. To make sure of complete curing, the specimens were put in an oven at 80 °C overnight.

2.3 Mechanical Testing

The reinforcement weight fraction was determined by the resin burn-off. The fiber volume fraction was measured from fiber, matrix, and composite density. Completion of the reaction was determined by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Some mechanical and thermal tests were performed to evaluate the matrix and flax, and glass reinforced PU composites properties. All mechanical tests were conducted at ambient temperature. Tensile strength and modulus, flexural strength and modulus, impact resistance, interlaminar shear strength were used to measure static mechanical properties. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was also used to determine thermal properties of specimens. DMA

Fig 1. Schematic chemical structure of the methoxylated sucrose soyate polyol (MSSP).

was carried out on a TA Instrument Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer at a heating rate of 5 °C /min from 0 to 190 °C with oscillation frequency of 10 Hz. The following sections provide details on the mechanical property testing that was carried out on neat PU and flax, and glass fiber reinforced bio-based PU composites.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Curing Analysis

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) is a useful tool for the characterization of curing reactions. Curing reactions are invariably exothermic processes and register in a DSC thermogram as an increase in specific heat (i.e. as an exotherm). The area under such peaks can be measured in terms of calories per gram of sample, and thus the DSC technique is used to obtain curing data with respect to temperature, i.e. the temperature at which a system starts to cure and a range over which it continues. Therefore, DSC verifies that the resin curing reaction was completed before any mechanical tests. A DSC Q1000 from TA Instruments with an auto sampler was used to measure the exothermic heat (heat per mass of material, J/g) when samples were subjected to a heat cycle from 0 to 260 °C by ramping at 10 °C/min.

DSC was started just after preparing the mixture, which is because the total heat of reaction is measured from 0% to 100% conversion. The residual heat was measured after isothermally curing in an oven at 80 °C for 4 hrs and at room temperature for 12 hrs. Fig. 2 shows the DSC for neat MSSP PU system for (1) from the beginning of the reaction, (2) after 4 hrs curing in an oven, and (3) after 12 hrs curing at room temperature. Based on these curves, to complete cure, the PU system requires more than 4 hours of postcuring at 80 °C. The degree of cure of PU system can be calculated by Eqn. (1):

$$\alpha_t = \frac{\Delta H_{\text{reaction}} - \Delta H_{\text{Residual}}}{\Delta H_{\text{reaction}}} = \frac{\Delta H_t}{\Delta H_{\text{reaction}}} \quad (1)$$

where α_t denotes the degree of cure at curing time t (hr), ΔH_t is the liberated heat during time t , ΔH_{res} is the residual heat after time t , and ΔH_{rxn} is the total heat of reaction. The integrated area of the exothermic peak was determined as the liberated heat in the DSC scan. The total heat of reaction (ΔH_{rxn}) and the residual heat after curing (ΔH_{res}) were obtained. Table 1 presents the degree of cure for neat MSSP PU with postcuring at 80 °C for 4 hours and at room temperature for 12 hours.

Fig. 2. DSC curves at 10 °C/min for neat MSSP PU system curing.

Table 1. The Degree of Cure of MSSP PU Systems

Sample	Curing condition	$\Delta H_{\text{residual}}$	$\Delta H_{\text{reaction}}$	Degree of Cure
Neat MSSP PU	4 hr at 80 °C	6.89	182.8	96.2
Neat MSSP PU	12 hr at room temp.	7.09	182.8	96.1

3.2 Tensile Testing

Tensile test specimens were cut from the fabricated panels according to American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards in a laboratory room environment (23 °C, 50% relative humidity) to promote failure in the gage section. Tensile testing (ASTM D3039) was conducted on an Instron Q5567 load frame using a displacement rate of 2 mm/min (0.08 in/min) throughout the investigation. An extensometer was attached to the sample to measure strain in order to calculate the modulus. The tensile properties obtained from the ASTM D3039 testing are shown in Table 2. Tensile strength for composites were not reported in these results as failure of most specimens was outside of the gage section. Future studies will include the use of tabs to ensure proper tensile failure.

Table 2. Tensile Tests Results for Neat PU, 40 vol.% Flax/PU, and 50 vol. % Glass/PU Composites

Samples	Tensile Modulus GPa (ksi)	Tensile Strength MPa (ksi)
Neat PU	1.41 ± 0.002 (205 ± 0.31)	36.34 ± 1.03 (5.27 ± 0.150)
Flax/PU	20.31 ± 5.50 (2944.26 ± 797.70)	---
Glass/PU	50.1 ± 11.2 (7266.39 ± 1624.42)	--

3.3 Flexural Testing

The 3-point flexural testing of the neat PU, flax/PU, and glass/PU composites was conducted on the same tensile machine (Instron Q5567 load frame)

according to the ASTM standard D790. For all tests, the support span shall be 16 times the depth of the beam. The minimum overhang length of either side of the supporting rollers should not be less than 6.35 mm (¼ in).

Testing was conducted at room temperature on five different samples. Both flexural strength and modulus was determined (Table 3).

Table 3. Flexural test results for neat PU, 40 vol.% Flax/PU, and 50 vol. % Glass/PU composites

Sample	Flexural Modulus GPa (ksi)	Flexural Strength MPa (ksi)
Neat PU	1.18 ± 0.18 (171.61 ± 26.58)	51.55 ± 6.09 7.47 ± 0.88
Flax/PU	12.38 ± 1.33 (1795.52 ± 193.46)	177.34 ± 14.79 (25.72 ± 2.15)
Glass/PU	36.21 ± 1.4 (5251.81 ± 203.05)	591.90 ± 13.59 (85.85 ± 1.97)

3.4 Interfacial Properties

The interfacial properties of flax/PU composites were evaluated by short beam shear tests (ASTM D2344). The results of short beam shear tests of flax/PU and glass/PU composites are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Interfacial Properties of 40 vol.% Flax/PU and 50 vol. % Glass/PU Composite

Sample	Interlaminar Shear Strength MPa (ksi)
Flax/PU	18.29 ± 0.742 (2.65 ± 0.11)
Glass/PU	40.22 ± 2.11 (5.83 ± 0.31)

3.5 Izod impact test (ASTM 256)

The test specimen for Izod impact is clamped into position so that the notched end of the specimen is facing the striking edge of the pendulum. The pendulum hammer is released, allowed to strike the specimen, and swing through. If the specimen does not break more weight is added to the hammer and the test is repeated until failure occurs. The impact values are directly read from the scale. Tinius Olsen impact testing machine used for measuring impact toughness. Assuming negligible friction and aerodynamic drag, the energy absorbed by the

specimen was equal to the height difference times the weight of the pendulum. The mean impact toughness for neat PU, flax/PU, and glass/PU composite specimens are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Unnotched impact toughness of neat PU, 40 vol.% Flax/PU, and 50 vol. % Glass/PU Composites

Sample	Impact Resistance J/m (ft-lb/in)
Neat PU	87.54 ± 33.62 (1.64 ± 0.63)
Flax/PU	587.3 ± 36.37 (11.0 ± 0.68)
Glass/PU	3933.55 ± 318.98 (73.56 ± 5.96)

3.6 T_g by DMA

Dynamic mechanical tests were carried out on a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA). The loss moduli and tan δ were recorded from 25 °C to 180 °C, at the heating rate of 5 °C/min (Table 6).

A typical plot of the temperature dependence of the storage modulus (G') of the high functionality soy polyol-based polyurethane and its composites are shown in Fig. 3. The value of G' was initially stable at low temperature (glassy state). Then, it sharply drops in the region between 70 and 130 °C. As the temperature further increased, G' stabilize in the rubbery state. The presence of a region where the storage modulus remains relatively constant indicates that a stable crosslinked network exists. The patterns of the curves of temperature dependence for the composite specimens are similar in nature to the neat polyurethane. However, over the temperature range studied, G' is noticeably increased in the flax and especially glass composites. The substantially increase in G' in composites is attributed to fiber loading and stress transfer at the matrix-fiber interface, thereby increasing the stiffness of the overall material.

A comparison of the average G' values measured at 40 °C is shown in Fig. 3. At this temperature, G' increased from an average of 7500 MPa in 40 vol % flax fiber reinforced with MSSP based polyurethane to 28750 MPa in the 50 vol% glass fiber reinforced with MSSP based polyurethane. These values represent significant improvements compared to the neat MSSP based polyurethane (1875 MPa).

Fig. 3. Temperature dependence of the storage modulus (G') of MSSP based polyurethane composites: (A) neat polyurethane, (B) flax reinforced (40 vol%) and (C) glass reinforced (50 vol%).

Fig. 4. Glass transition temperature (T_g) of MSSP based polyurethanes composites: (A) neat polyurethane, (B) flax reinforced (40 vol%) and (C) glass reinforced (50 vol%)

The glass transition temperatures (T_g) were determined from the peak of the $\tan \delta$ (ratio of loss modulus, G'' , to storage modulus, G') curves. Only one T_g (112.11 ± 1.8) was observed for the polyurethane suggesting a single phase system. The high T_g of these composites containing sucrose soyate was attributed to the great structural

rigidity and the high functionality of the sucrose molecule which is the core of sucrose soyate. The rigidity of the sucrose molecule has been shown to give more rigid thermosets in previous studies [2, 18].

Flax/PU exhibited higher glass transition temperature than the glass/PU composites. However the error bars overlap, thus indicating that glass transition temperature may be the same in both the flax and glass composites. Considering fiber loading that is 25 vol% less in flax fiber compared to glass fiber, the T_g of this biobased polyurethane shifted to higher values and was determined to be 117.31 ± 0.58 °C for the flax-reinforced composite if considering the error bar, no increase was noticed when E-glass was used as reinforcement (114.31 ± 2.8).

The increase in T_g for the flax/PU composites suggests a restricted mobility of polymer chains in the network. This may be the result of the increased number of hydroxyl groups available on the flax fiber. Those groups react with isocyanate and result in immobilization of polyurethane molecules on fibers. The intensity of $\tan \delta$ decreases in composites due to the net volume reduction of the polyurethane resin but also as a result of the lower chain mobility (Fig. 4).

Table 6. T_g for neat PU, 40 vol.% Flax/PU, and 50 vol. % Glass/PU composite

Sample	T_g °C (°F)
Neat PU	112.11 ± 1.8 (233.79 ± 3.24)
Flax/PU	117.31 ± 0.58 (243.16 ± 1.04)
Glass/ PU	114.31 ± 2.8 (250.18 ± 5.04)

3.7 Heat Deflection Temperature

The heat distortion temperature (HDT), usually denotes the highest temperature to which a polymer may be used as a rigid material in application, which is why HDT sometimes is referred to as softening temperature. Up to this maximum temperature (HDT), a material is able to support a load for some appreciable time. Heat distortion temperature was determined using a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) using a three-point bending fixture. According to ASTM International Standard D 648, the samples were heated from 25 °C temperature to 300 °C at the rate of 3 °C/min Table 7 shows the

HDT for neat PU, the flax/PU composite, and glass/PU composite.

Table 7. HDT for neat PU, 40 vol.% Flax/PU, and 50 vol. % Glass/PU composite

Sample	HDT °C (°F)
Neat PU	68.8 ± 1.8 (155.84 ± 3.24)
Flax/PU	243.67 ± 6.03 (470.61 ± 10.85)
Glass/ PU	274.32 ± 2.8 (525.78 ± 5.04)

4 Conclusion

The static mechanical properties (i.e. tensile strength, flexural strength, and impact strength) and thermal properties (HDT, T_g) were investigated for 40 vol.% flax/PU, and 50 vol. % glass/PU composite. Although the volume fraction of flax fiber was lower than fiberglass reinforced composites, they exhibit comparable thermal properties to the fiberglass reinforced composites. By considering the lower volume fraction of flax in composites, they were also found to exhibit mechanical properties comparable to that of a commercially available fiberglass/PU composite. Future studies will be conducted on composites with similar fiber volume fractions for improved comparison.

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6 References

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